

Trust In Ad Media

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Abstract—Advertising today has already become an integral part of human life as a building block of the consumer community. A component of the value chain of the media, advertising sector is struggling increasingly harder to find new methods to reach consumers. The tendency towards experimental marketing practices is increasing day by day, especially to divert consumers from the idea “They are selling something to me.” It is therefore considered a good idea to investigate the trust in ad media of consumers, who are today exposed to a great bulk of information from advertising sector.

In this study, the current value of ad media for the young consumer will be investigated. Data on various ad media reliability will be comparatively analyzed and young consumers will be traced by including university students in the study. In this research, which will be performed on students studying at the Selçuk University (Turkey) by random sampling method, data will be obtained by survey technique and evaluated by a statistical analysis.

Keywords—Trust in advertising, ad medium, media.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

THE principal target of advertising is with no doubt to persuade the consumer into the consequence intended by the advertiser. A great many factors on the side of the consumer are present, influencing the formation of the emotion, thought or behavior desired as a result of ad communication. As well as such mental processes as perception, learning, recall, establishing an attitude and being persuaded, certain personal factors such as liking the ad or finding it trustworthy have a great part to play on the consumers. The main focus of this study is the trust in the ad among the factors with respect to consumers.

As part of the typical behavior of consumers, the consumers attempt to obtain information in several ways to make the most accurate decision regarding the services and goods they will make use of. Among the factors that affect this process are several aspects such as skepticism, belief and trust. It is of great importance for these aspects to be in the favorable direction in order to make the most accurate decision as regards the purchasing [1]

Trust is a complicated and multi-faceted structure. In terms of advertising literature, such diverse concepts as credibility, trustworthiness, truthfulness, and believability are regarded as the constituents of the feeling trust. It is an evaluation mostly directed to the whole ad. There are various points of view regarding the concepts of credibility and trust in the literature of advertising and the interrelationship between them. Credibility is only related to a section of trust in advertising.

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Credibility on its own isn't found sufficient to show the quality and extent of trust in advertising [2], [3].

Credibility in advertising is measured and conceptualized in four ways. These are source credibility, i.e. trustworthiness and expertise, advertising credibility in the general sense, ad content credibility, i.e. perceptions that ad-claims are truthful and believable, and media credibility [2].

Maloney marks that ad believability is the obvious expression of the ad effect on the mind of the viewer. Credibility is realized through the interactive process in which the attitudes that viewers have collected from their previous experiences and the memory intertwine. Individuals display differing trustworthiness reactions to differing ads since they have developed differing grounding and differing feelings towards the brands and goods being advertised. It follows that while an ad may be thoroughly believable for one individual, it may simply not be believable for another [4].

Obermiller and Spangler contributed to the credibility of ads with the concept of “ad skepticism”. They defined this concept as the tendency not to believe the informative propositions of the ad [5]. Ad skepticism directs the inclination of not believing the ad. Because a high level of ad skepticism creates the feeling of not trusting the ad, consumers gain grounds for refusing the ad and being informed about the goods [6]. In the study conducted by Obermiller, Spangenberg, and MacLachlan to examine the relation between skepticism towards the ad and the reaction to the ad, it was established that skeptics were in general less favorable towards their reactions to the ad. However, it was concluded that skeptics avoid the ad when they made a connection between the ad and the purchase [6].

Several other studies were conducted regarding the attitudes towards the ad and the advertiser (within the context of belief) apart from the previous ones [7]-[10]. In these studies too, it was concluded that, in general, the reactions to the ad increased adversely as the attitude towards or belief in the ad or advertiser weakened.

In another study carried out by Prendergast, Liu and Poon, conclusion were drawn regarding the ads of which products or services consumers didn't find credible and to which medium of advertising this applied more. According to this study, the ads of the products that make you lose weight were found less credible. The radio and television were identified to be the most credible, while direct mail and the internet were the least trusted media [11].

In still another study conducted by Soh, Reid and King, the aim was to reveal the characteristic and extent of trust in advertising. The relationship of trust in advertising with such similar patterns as advertising credibility was questioned, and a scale called ADTRUST was developed (Table I) [2], [3].

TABLE I
 THE ADTRUST SCALE

Components	Information conveyed in TV advertising is.....
Reliability	1.Honest
	2.Truthful
	3.Credible
	4.Reliable
	5.Dependable
	6.Accurate
	7.Factual
	8.Complete
	9.Clear
	10.Valuable
Usefulness	11.Good
	12.Useful
	13.Helps people make the best decisions
Affect	14.Likeable
	15.Enjoyable
Willingness to Rely On	16.Positive
	17. I am willing to rely on ad-conveyed information when making purchase-related decisions.
	18. I am willing to make important purchase-related decisions based on ad-conveyed information.
	19. I am willing to consider the ad-conveyed information when making purchase-related decisions.
	20. I am willing to recommend the product or service that I have seen in ads to my friends or family.

Soh, Reid and King expressed the findings they obtained in the study out of which they developed the ADTRUST scale as follows [2]:

“The study found that (1) the ADTRUST Scale exhibited sufficient reliability and concurrent, convergent, discriminant, and nomological validity; (2) trust in advertising is a multi-dimensional construct (i.e., cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions) with four distinct factors (reliability, usefulness, affect, and willingness to rely on), which reflect a combination of (a) consumer perception of reliability and usefulness of advertising, (b) consumer affect toward advertising, and (c) consumer willingness to rely on advertising for decisions making, (3) trust in advertising and advertising credibility are separate and independent constructs; and (4) trust should be operationalized and measured as an independent, three-factor structure (i.e., reliability and usefulness=cognitive dimension; affect=emotional dimension; and willingness to rely on=behavioral dimension) in advertising research. The last two findings are especially important to this investigation.”

According to the results of the study conducted by Soh, Reid, and King, consumers don't feel strong trust in the ad media. Based on the findings regarding the level of trust towards the ad media, it is seen that the trust in the ads on the internet are far lower compared with those in other medium. Consumers find the medium of the net less reliable than the other conventional ad media [2].

The ADTRUST scale, developed by Soh, Reid, and King (2007), was used in a study conducted on university students at the Selçuk University in Turkey. It was aimed through the study to measure the trust level of the students towards the ad media in Turkey.

Attempts will be made to reveal the answers to the following questions;

1. The level of trust in general towards the ad

2. The levels of trust with respect to the media
3. The comparison of the trust level towards the ad and the trust towards the ad media
4. The levels of trust with respect to the sex and the income level

II. METHODOLOGY

The data of the study were collected from students at the Selçuk University. The data were gathered with the survey method in the study in which random sampling method was used. Approximately 45 thousand students study at the Selçuk University campus, which has 74 thousand students in total. The data in this study were obtained from 431 students studying at 13 different faculties in the campus.

The survey consisted of 147 questions, of which 140 were designed to measure the trust level towards the ad and the advertiser, and of which the remaining 7 were designed to gather the demographic data.

The questions of the study are grouped in this way;

- the questions that measure the level of trust towards the ad in general
- the questions that measure the level of trust towards 6 different ad media (television, newspaper, radio, magazine, internet and outdoor)
- the questions that measure the demographic data

The questions to measure the levels of trust were designed through the ADTRUST scale mentioned in the literature section of the study. 7-point Likert scale was used in getting the answers to the questions (1 strongly disagree- strongly agree 7). The data were calculated through SPSS statistical program and reported.

III. RESULTS

The findings obtained as a result of the analysis of the data collected from the participants in the study were shown in this section and interpreted.

TABLE II
 THE DISTRIBUTION OF THE PARTICIPANTS WITH RESPECT TO THE SEX

Sex	Frequency	Valid Percent
Female	230	55.2
Male	187	44.8
Missing	14	
Total	431	100

Of the 431 participants from whom the findings were collected, 55.2 % were female and 44.8 % were male.

TABLE III
 THE LEVELS OF TRUST FOR THE AD MEDIA

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. D.
Advertising	431	1	7	3.18	1.06
Television	430	1	7	3.27	1.23
Newspaper	429	1	7	3.45	1.20
Radio	423	1	7	3.02	1.23
Magazine	424	1	7	3.32	1.21
Internet	427	1	7	2.93	1.45
Outdoor	419	1	7	3.32	1.29
Valid N (list-wise)	411				

The levels of trust in the ad media were revealed in accordance with the data obtained in the study. Accordingly, the level of trust in newspaper ads ($\bar{X}=3.45$) was higher than that towards the other ad media. It is followed by the magazine ads ($\bar{X}=3.32$) and outdoors ads ($\bar{X}=3.32$). The ad medium with the lowest level of trust is the internet ($\bar{X}=2.93$). The level of trust in the ad in general was identified to be at an average level ($\bar{X}=3.18$).

TABLE IV
BETWEEN GROUPS ANOVA FOR THE LEVEL OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND THE LEVELS OF TRUST IN THE AD MEDIA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Tv					
Betw G	444,134	126	3.525	5.153	.000
Within G	207,279	303	.684		
Total	651,413	429			
News.					
Betw G	363,881	126	2.888	3.331	.000
Within G	261,816	302	.867		
Total	625,697	428			
Radio					
Betw G	390,341	124	3.148	3.692	.000
Within G	254,105	298	.853		
Total	644,446	422			
Magaz.					
Betw G	389,639	124	3.142	4.000	.000
Within G	234,905	299	.786		
Total	624,544	423			
Internet					
Betw G	453,583	125	3.629	2.455	.000
Within G	444,924	301	1.478		
Total	898,507	426			
Outdoor					
Betw G	341,199	125	2.730	2.228	.000
Within G	359,039	293	1.225		
Total	700,238	418			

There is a significant correlation between the level of trust in TV ads ($F=5.15$; df 126; $p<.05$), the level of trust in newspaper ads ($F=3.33$; df 126; $p<.05$), the level of trust in radio ads ($F=3.69$; df 124; $p<.05$), the level of trust in magazine ads ($F=4.00$; df 124; $p<.05$), the level of trust in outdoors ads ($F=2.22$; df 125; $p<.05$) and the level of trust in the ad in general.

TABLE V
THE COMPARISON OF THE LEVELS OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND IN THE AD MEDIA

PAIRED SAMPLES CORRELATIONS			
	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair1 trust in ad & Television	430	.739	.000
Pair2 trust in ad & Newspaper	429	.598	.000
Pair3 trust in ad & Radio	423	.567	.000

TABLE VIII
THE T TEST LEVELS OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND IN THE AD MEDIA WITH RESPECT TO SEXES

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. 2-tailed	Mean Difference
Advertising	.028	.868				
Equal variances Assumed			-1.839	415	.067	-.1896
Equal variances not assumed			-1.837	395.689	.067	-.1896

Pair4 trust in ad & Magazine	424	.648	.000
Pair5 trust in ad & Internet	427	.497	.000
Pair6 trust in ad & Outdoor	419	.510	.000

TABLE VI
THE COMPARISON OF THE LEVELS OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND IN THE AD MEDIA

PAIRED SAMPLES CORRELATIONS						
	Mean	Std. D	Mean	t	df	Sig.
Pair1	-.0859	.84522	0.4076	-2.106	429	.036
TV& Trust in ad						
Pair2	-.2729	1.0281	.04964	-5.499	428	.000
New& trust in ad						
Pair3	.1544	1.08162	.05259	2.935	422	.004
Rad& trust in ad						
Pair4	-.1513	.9663	.0469	-3.225	423	.001
Mag& trust in ad						
Pair5	.2569	1.30635	.06322	4.063	426	.000
Int& trust in ad						
Pair6	-.1530	1.17951	.05762	-2.656	418	.008
Out& trust in ad						

According to the results of the correlation analysis to determine the power and direction of the relationship between the level of trust in the ad and the levels of trust in different ad media, it is seen that a significant correlation exists between the variables.

When the results of the correlation analysis to determine the power and direction of the relationship between the level of trust in general advertising and the level of trust in TV ads are examined, it appears that there is a strong and significant correlation in a positive direction between the two variables ($r=.739$; $p<.05$). In other words, as the trust in TV ads increases, there is in general an increase in the level of trust towards the general ad.

TABLE VII
THE LEVELS OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND IN THE AD MEDIA WITH RESPECT TO SEXES

	N	Mean	Std.D.	Std.Error Mean
Advertising Female	230	3,08	1,04075	,06863
Male	187	3,27	1,05453	,07711
Television Female	230	3,16	1,25724	,08290
Male	186	3,37	1,17192	,08593
Newspaper Female	229	3,34	1,27007	,08393
Male	186	3,60	1,13331	,08310
Radio Female	230	2,96	1,22225	,08059
Male	180	3,12	1,24479	,09278
Magazine Female	230	3,21	1,23893	,08169
Male	180	3,46	1,18578	,08838
Internet Female	229	2,90	1,51354	,10002
Male	185	2,96	1,38499	,10183
Outdoor Female	228	3,12	1,29929	,08605
Male	184	3,56	1,25044	,09218

Television	.817	.367				
Equal variances Assumed			-1.789	414	.074	-.2152
Equal variances not assumed			-1.802	405.708	.072	-.2152
Newspaper	4.170	.042				
Equal variances Assumed			-2.141	413	.033	-.2559
Equal variances not assumed			-2.167	409.330	.031	-.2559
Radio	.175	.676				
Equal variances Assumed			-1.279	408	.202	-.1569
Equal variances not assumed			-1.276	381.331	.203	-.1569
Magazine	.904	.342				
Equal variances Assumed			-2.021	408	.044	-.2445
Equal variances not assumed			-2.031	391.910	.043	-.2445
Internet	1.942	.164				
Equal variances Assumed			-.396.-	412	.692	-.0571
Equal variances not assumed			.400	405.618	.690	-.0571
Outdoor	2.355	.126				
Equal variances Assumed			-3.493	410	.001	-.4442
Equal variances not assumed			-3.507	397.530	.001	-.4442

The level of trust in the newspaper ads with respect to the sex of the participants shows a remarkable variation. When the table for multi-comparison is examined ($t=-2.14$; $df=413$; $p<.05$), males attach more importance to the level of trust in the newspaper ads with an arithmetic mean of 3.60, compared with females ($\bar{X}=3.34$). The level of trust by males and females in the medium of newspaper was found to be higher, compared with the other ad media. It was established that males had a higher level of trust compared with females with an arithmetic mean in all levels of trust except for the internet.

TABLE IX
THE ANOVA BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF TRUST IN THE GENERAL AD AND THE AD MEDIUM AND THE LEVEL OF INCOME

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Advertising					
Between Groups	6,206	3	2.069	1.898	.129
Within Groups	448,943	412	1.090		
Total	455,149	415			
Television					
Between Groups	6,569	3	2.190	1.471	.222
Within Groups	611,792	411	1.489		
Total	618,361	414			
Newspaper					
Between Groups	1,153	3	.384	.260	.854
Within Groups	606,665	410	1.480		
Total	607,818	413			
Radio					
Between Groups	2,334	3	.778	.512	.674
Within Groups	614,893	405	1.518		
Total	617,228	408			
Magazine					
Between Groups	11,051	3	3.684	2.516	.058
Within Groups	592,880	405	1.464		
Total	603,931	408			
Internet					
Between Groups	3,142	3	1.047	.491	.689
Within Groups	872,008	409	2.132		
Total	875,150	412			
Outdoor					
Between Groups	8,532	3	2.844	1.693	.168
Within Groups	683,861	407	1.680		
Total	692,393	410			

There is no significant correlation between the level of trust in the ad in general ($f=1.89$; $p<.05$), the level of trust in TV ads ($f=1.47$; $p<.05$), the level of trust in newspaper ads ($f=.26$; $p<.05$), the level of trust in radio ads ($f=.512$; $p<.05$), the level of trust in magazine ads ($f=2.51$; $p<.05$), the level of trust in

the internet ($f=.491$; $p<.05$), and the level of trust in outdoors ads ($f=1.69$; $p<.05$).

TABLE X
THE DISTRIBUTION OF TRUST ITEMS TOWARDS THE GENERAL AD AND THE AD MEDIA

Trust Items	TV M	News M	Rad. M	Mag. M	Int. M	Out. M	Ad. M
1	2.82	3.47	2.92	3.09	2.58	3.16	2.85
2	3.02	3.62	2.98	3.23	2.74	3.24	3.18
3	2.99	3.46	2.98	3.24	2.71	3.29	3.00
4	3.00	3.53	2.95	3.24	2.68	3.24	2.95
5	3.01	3.49	2.97	3.16	2.64	3.24	2.85
6	2.77	3.09	2.86	2.98	2.58	3.14	2.55
7	3.01	3.43	3.03	3.25	2.70	3.29	2.85
8	2.93	3.19	2.86	3.09	2.70	3.08	2.60
9	3.26	3.51	3.09	3.41	2.88	3.32	3.03
10	3.28	3.58	3.11	3.49	3.03	3.39	3.23
11	3.45	3.71	3.28	3.62	3.09	3.52	3.52
12	3.39	3.70	3.11	3.63	3.16	3.49	3.54
13	3.31	3.35	3.02	3.21	3.09	3.28	3.08
14	4.01	3.61	3.35	3.77	3.56	3.79	4.13
15	4.43	3.63	3.53	3.91	3.71	3.81	4.54
16	3.76	3.68	3.23	3.68	3.36	3.67	3.65
17	3.27	3.29	2.76	3.13	2.89	3.17	2.87
18	3.20	3.15	2.74	3.06	2.75	3.02	2.84
19	3.23	3.20	2.73	3.10	2.81	3.13	3.23
20	3.13	3.21	2.72	3.12	2.81	3.10	3.10

The Trust Items in the Table X (shown with numbers) are shown in the Table XI.

TABLE XI
THE TRUST ITEMS

1.Honest
2.Truthful
3.Credible
4.Reliable
5.Dependable
6.Accurate
7.Factual
8.Complete
9.Clear
10.Valuable
11.Good
12.Useful
13.Helps people make the best decisions
14.Likeable
15.Enjoyable
16.Positive
17. I am willing to rely on ad-conveyed information when making purchase-related decisions.

18. I am willing to make important purchase-related decisions based on ad-conveyed information.
19. I am willing to consider the ad-conveyed information when making purchase-related decisions.
20. I am willing to recommend the product or service that I have seen in ads to my friends or family.

TABLE XII
THE DISTRIBUTION OF TRUST COMPONENTS TOWARDS THE GENERAL AD AND THE AD MEDIA

Trust Comp.	Ad. M	TV. M	New s. M	Rad. M	Mag. M	Int. M	Out. M
Reliability	2.87	2.98	3.42	2.96	3.19	2.69	3.23
Usefulness	3.35	3.37	3.59	3.15	3.49	3.10	3.41
Affect	4.11	4.07	3.65	3.37	3.78	3.54	3.76
Willingness to Rely On (purchase-related)	3.06	3.21	3.22	2.73	3.10	2.82	3.10

When the arithmetic mean of the components constituting trust is taken according to the ad and the ad media, it is established that “reliability” is the highest in the newspaper ($\bar{X}=3.42$), that “usefulness” is similarly the highest in the newspaper ($\bar{X}=3.59$), that “affect” is directed most towards the ad ($\bar{X}=4.11$) and towards the TV and that “willingness to rely on” is the highest in the newspaper ($\bar{X}=3.22$) and TV ($\bar{X}=3.21$). It is revealed that “reliability” is the lowest in the internet ($\bar{X}=2.69$) and in the trust in advertising ($\bar{X}=2.87$), that “usefulness” is the lowest in the internet ($\bar{X}=3.10$) and radio ($\bar{X}=3.15$), that “affect” is the lowest in the radio ($\bar{X}=3.37$) and that “willingness to rely on” is the lowest in the radio ($\bar{X}=2.73$) and internet ($\bar{X}=2.82$).

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, which was carried out to measure the levels of trust in the ad media and at the same time the level of trust in the advertising in general, the following findings were obtained on the whole;

- The levels of trust in the advertising among the participants in general can be judged as at an average level.
- The participants have the highest trust in newspaper ads. They can make purchase-related decisions, depending on the information they have obtained from this medium. The newspaper medium is followed by the magazine and outdoors. It can be concluded from these evaluations that the participants have the highest trust in the printed media. The ad media with the lowest level of trust for the participants is the internet.
- Significant correlations have been found between the level of trust in the ad and the level of trust in the ad media. The strongest correlation among them is the one with the television advertising. As the level of trust in television ads increases, an increase is observed in general in the level of trust in advertising.
- When the levels of trust are examined in accordance with the demographic variables of the participants, it is seen that males have a higher level of trust in all the media, except in the internet, than females. Females have more

confidence in the internet, in which the participants have the lowest level of trust among all media, than males. No significant correlation has been found between the participants’ level of income and their levels of trust in advertising and in the ad media.

- Another significant point the study has revealed has been obtained through the comparison of trust components with the advertising and the ad media. In this way, whereas the medium with the highest level of trust is the newspaper, the highest level of “affect” is seen in the ad media and television. In this sense, it can be said about the newspaper that it is an ad medium with a high level of reliability and usefulness, emotionally not very influential yet considered useful in the purchase- and recommendation-related decisions. It can be said about the television that while it has a low level of reliability and an average level of usefulness, it is important in terms of “affect” and taken into consideration in purchase- and recommendation-related decisions. It may be reasonable to interpret this conclusion in this way; the participants may feel trust in the ad media with differing cognitive or emotional attitudes regarding their purchase- or recommendation-related decisions. When compared with the other ad media, internet and radio, found to have a low level of reliability and usefulness, were also found to have a lower level of “affect” and a higher level of “unwillingness to rely on purchase- and recommendation-related decisions.

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